

VARIATIONAL APPROACH BASED CRACKED LAMINATE ANALYSES REVISITED

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SUMMARY

The analyses of cracked laminates based on a variational principle are appraised. The limitations of existing analyses of more general laminate configurations have been identified and overcome. A well posed boundary value problem has been formulated. The capability of analysing cracked laminates has been enhanced.

Keywords: cracked laminate analysis; variational approach; total complementary potential energy; periodic conditions; translational symmetry; natural boundary conditions

INTRODUCTION

The capability of micromechanical stress analysis of a cracked laminate has evolved over decades to build up in terms of accuracy and versatility, from ply-discount in early days to shear-lag [1], variational approach [2], stress transfer [3], finite elements [4] and finite strips [5]. The outcome of such micromechanical stress analyses offer supports to other approaches in damage mechanics, such as self-consistent approach [6] and continuum damage mechanics [7-9]. The present paper is to re-examine the variational approach first published by Hashin [2], which had probably been preceded [10] and definitely succeeded by many attempts, e.g. [11-14], in the endeavour to understand the damage characteristics of laminated composites. Among this approach, shear lag and stress transfer, there is a commonality. The mathematical model involves effectively only two layers, one cracked and one uncracked, representing a three-layered laminate after the application of symmetry considerations. In some attempts, the uncracked layer has been generalised to an orthotropic sub-laminate [13,14] in order to make the model more adaptable. Along the line of these approaches, no attempt has been found in the literature to extend the capability to the analysis of laminates with multiple cracked and uncracked layers, which cannot be simplified to a two-layer model using symmetry. For example, for a $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$ laminate with both 90° plies cracked, one would still be left with three layers even after the use of mid-plane symmetry. Existing approaches may find difficult to deal with it without making rough approximations.

The so-called variational approach, as in [2,12,13,15], as well as the analysis to be presented later in this paper, is a semi-variational approach, in fact, strictly speaking. A variational principle, *viz.* the minimum total complementary potential energy (TCPE) principle, has been employed, not to solve the problem of cracked laminate analysis completely, but only partially aiming at eliminating the dependence of the problem on the coordinate in the thickness direction of the laminate, so that the problem can be reduced to a one-dimensional boundary value problem dependent only on one

coordinate in the longitudinal direction of the laminate. The governing ordinary differential equation(s) for the boundary value problem is obtained as the Euler's equation(s) from the variational calculus. The solution of the boundary value problem is independent of the variational process, where analytical (when the problem is simple enough) or numerical (when it exceeds a level of complexity) methods have to be employed. In general, the more layers involved, the more equations will emerge. However, the difficulty in existing analyses as boundary value problems is not because of increased number of ordinary differential equations involved. Rather, it is because of the lack of appropriate boundary conditions to determine the solution mathematically from the physical construction of the laminate. This will be elaborated in the paper to draw a clear borderline to define the applicability of the existing approach.

The development here will break this barrier by supplementing the much needed boundary conditions from the natural boundary conditions of variational calculus. The variational approach based analysis of cracked laminates can be formulated as a well posed boundary value problem mathematically, however many cracked and uncracked laminae are involved. This enhances the capability of analysing cracked laminates.

FORMULATION

The problem will be formulated in the context of an arbitrary layup laminate as sketched in Fig. 1 where the coordinate system is defined. The total thickness is assumed to be h and the total number of laminae n . The z -coordinate of the l^{th} interface, i.e. the one between the l^{th} and $(l+1)^{\text{th}}$ laminae, is denoted as z_l , ($l=1, 2, \dots, n$), with those for the bottom and top surfaces denoted as z_0 and z_n , respectively. The laminate can be subjected to in-plane loading N and bending moment M , as shown. The strain-stress relationship can be given as follows for a 2D problem in the x - z plane

$$\{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}\} = \{\varepsilon_{xx} \quad \varepsilon_{zz} \quad \gamma_{xz}\}, \quad \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}\} = \{\sigma_{xx} \quad \sigma_{zz} \quad \sigma_{xz}\} \quad \text{and} \quad [S] = [S_{ij}] \quad (1)$$

where S_{ij} can be expressed in terms of material's engineering elastic constants depending on the stress state, plane stress or plane strain.

Fig. 1 A cracked laminate

When an elastic body is loaded before damage takes place, the stresses in it are assumed to be $\bar{\sigma}_i$ which can be obtained from a simple analysis using the classic laminate theory. Upon the emergence of damage in it, under the same loading, the stresses acquire a perturbation $\hat{\sigma}_i$ from $\bar{\sigma}_i$ and the total stresses become

$$\sigma_i = \bar{\sigma}_i + \hat{\sigma}_i \quad (i=1, 3, 5). \quad (2)$$

The complementary strain energy is obtained

$$U = \bar{U} + \hat{U} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} S_{ij} \bar{\sigma}_i \bar{\sigma}_j d\Omega + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} S_{ij} \hat{\sigma}_i \hat{\sigma}_j d\Omega \quad (3)$$

as the mixed term vanishes in general. It is assumed that the cracks developed in the laminate are transverse to the plane of the laminate across the full width of the laminate in the y -direction as shown in Fig. 1 as a cross-section perpendicular to the y -axis. The cracks are uniformly spaced $2a$ apart in the x -direction. The stresses in each lamina are

$$\sigma_{xx}^{(l)} = \bar{\sigma}_{xx}^{(l)} + \hat{\sigma}_{xx}^{(l)} \quad \sigma_{zz}^{(l)} = \hat{\sigma}_{zz}^{(l)} \quad \sigma_{xz}^{(l)} = \hat{\sigma}_{xz}^{(l)}. \quad l = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (4)$$

Denote the in-plane direct stress in the x -direction in the l^{th} lamina of the laminate before cracking and the perturbation to this stress as the unknown function

$$\bar{\sigma}_{xx}^{(l)} = \sigma_l \quad \hat{\sigma}_{xx}^{(l)} = -\sigma_l \phi_l(x) \quad l = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (5)$$

For the perturbation stress as assumed in (5) to be admissible for its use in the minimum TCPE principle, perturbation stresses $\hat{\sigma}_{xz}^{(l)}$ and $\hat{\sigma}_{zz}^{(l)}$, along with $\hat{\sigma}_{xx}^{(l)}$, have to satisfy all equilibrium conditions involving coordinate z , including traction boundary conditions. From the equilibrium equations the $\hat{\sigma}_{xz}^{(l)}$ and $\hat{\sigma}_{zz}^{(l)}$ can then be expressed in terms of ϕ_l

$$\hat{\sigma}_{xz}^{(l)} = -\sigma_l (\phi_l'(x)z + f_l(x)) \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{\sigma}_{zz}^{(l)} = -\sigma_l \left(\frac{1}{2} \phi_l''(x)z^2 + f_l'(x)z + g_l(x) \right) \quad (6)$$

where f_l and g_l are integration functions. To make these perturbation stresses admissible, the bottom and top surfaces have to be traction free and the continuity conditions across the interfaces should also be met. These will render the integration functions determined, leading to the perturbation stresses as expressed

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\sigma}_{xx}^{(l)} &= -\sigma_l \phi_l(x) & \hat{\sigma}_{xz}^{(l)} &= \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} (z_j - z_{j-1}) \sigma_j \phi_j'(x) + (z - z_{l-1}) \sigma_l \phi_l'(x) \\ \hat{\sigma}_{zz}^{(l)} &= \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} (z_j - z_{j-1}) \left(\frac{1}{2} (z_j + z_{j-1}) - z \right) \sigma_j \phi_j''(x) - \frac{1}{2} (z - z_{l-1})^2 \sigma_l \phi_l''(x) \end{aligned} \quad (l=1, 2, \dots, n) \quad (8)$$

where the summation terms will be taken as zero when the upper limit becomes zero (when $l=1$). It can be verified that the above stresses satisfy equilibrium equations and the traction free conditions on the bottom surface. Interlaminar stresses $\sigma_{xz}^{(l)}$ and $\sigma_{zz}^{(l)}$ are continuous across the interfaces. They are still subject to the top surface traction free conditions before becoming admissible for the application of the minimum TCPE principle, which have been found to be related to two global equilibrium conditions for the perturbation membrane force \hat{N} and bending moment about the y -axis \hat{M}

$$\hat{N} = -\sum_{l=1}^n (z_l - z_{l-1}) \sigma_l \phi_l(x) = 0 \quad \hat{M} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{l=1}^n (z_l^2 - z_{l-1}^2) \sigma_l \phi_l(x) = 0 \quad (8)$$

They cannot always be satisfied. For instance, in a two-layered asymmetric $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ laminate, the satisfaction of these conditions would require that ϕ_l be a linear function

of x (with vanishing 2nd order derivative). This would conflict with the physical boundary conditions for ϕ_l as will be presented later. This draws a limit of the applicability of any approach in which $\sigma_{xx}^{(l)}$ is assumed to remain constant in the z -direction in each lamina. (8) apply to laminates having at least three laminae and the simplest case is a symmetric three-layered laminate as addressed in [2]. For asymmetric laminates with n (>2) laminae, out of a set of n unknowns ϕ_l , ($l=1,2,\dots,n$), two can be eliminated using (8). For symmetric laminates with n (>1) laminae in the symmetric half laminate under symmetric loading, one out of n unknowns ϕ_l ($l=1,2,\dots,n$) can be eliminated using the first of (8). The remaining unknowns will be denoted as $\{\phi\}$ hereafter in this paper and they are the independent unknown functions for the mathematical formulation of the problem. A lamina corresponding to an independent unknown function will be referred to as an ‘independent lamina’.

The TCPE is the sum of the complementary strain energy and the potential of prescribed displacements. For the present problem, the latter is absent. It is clear that only the perturbation TCPE will contribute to the variation

$$\hat{\Gamma} = \int_{-a}^a F(x, \{\phi\}, \{\phi'\}, \{\phi''\}) dx \quad (9)$$

$$\text{where } F(x, \{\phi\}, \{\phi'\}, \{\phi''\}) = \{\phi\}^T [C^{00}] \{\phi\} + 2\{\phi\}^T [C^{01}] \{\phi'\} + 2\{\phi\}^T [C^{02}] \{\phi''\} \\ + \{\phi'\}^T [C^{11}] \{\phi'\} + 2\{\phi'\}^T [C^{12}] \{\phi''\} + \{\phi''\}^T [C^{22}] \{\phi''\}. \quad (10)$$

Coefficient matrices $[C^{00}]$, etc., with the superscripts corresponding to the orders of derivatives of $\{\phi\}$ involved, can be evaluated systematically. When a variation is taken for the TCPE, the stationary value condition, $\delta\Gamma = 0$, leads to the Euler’s equations as the governing equations for the problem as follows.

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial \{\phi\}} - \frac{d}{dx} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \{\phi'\}} + \frac{d^2}{dx^2} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \{\phi''\}} = 0$$

$$\text{or } [A_4] \{\phi''''(x)\} + [A_3] \{\phi'''(x)\} + [A_2] \{\phi''(x)\} + [A_1] \{\phi'(x)\} + [A_0] \{\phi(x)\} = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\text{where } [A_4] = [C^{22}], \quad [A_3] = [C^{12}]^T - [C^{12}], \\ [A_2] = [C^{02}]^T + [C^{02}] - [C^{11}], \quad [A_1] = [C^{01}] - [C^{01}]^T, \quad [A_0] = [C^{00}]. \quad (12)$$

The presence of terms of odd orders of derivatives in (11) is associated with the presence of off-axis laminae. They introduce a restriction on the analytical solutions. The governing equations (11) are 4th order ordinary differential equations. If one seeks analytical solutions, the limit would be a single 4th order differential equation in (11) in presence of odd order derivatives or two in absence of odd order derivatives. This implies that there can only be a single independent lamina in the laminate if it contains off-axis laminae, or two if the laminate is cross-ply, in general.

The mathematical problem associated with the ordinary differential equations is a boundary value problem. Boundary conditions are required in order to solve it.

PHYSICAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

To determine the solution for (11), four boundary conditions are required for each independent unknown, in general, given the order of the governing equations. For a cracked lamina, there are four boundary conditions readily available, i.e.

$$\sigma_{xx}(\pm a, z) = \sigma_{xz}(\pm a, z) = 0. \quad (13)$$

However, for an uncracked lamina, the physical conditions available can only produce three boundary conditions. Take the transverse shear stress σ_{xz} from the free body diagram as shown in Fig. 2, to start with. The continuity consideration leads to

$$\sigma_{xz}^1 = \sigma_{xz}^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{xz}^3 = \sigma_{xz}^4 \quad (14)$$

while the periodic condition or translational symmetry requires

$$\sigma_{xz}^1 = \sigma_{xz}^3 \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{xz}^2 = \sigma_{xz}^4 \quad (15)$$

$$\text{thus} \quad \sigma_{xz}^2 = \sigma_{xz}^3 \quad \text{or} \quad \sigma_{xz}(+a, z) = \sigma_{xz}(-a, z). \quad (16)$$

The same argument applies to the direct stress, leading to a boundary condition

$$\sigma_{xx}(+a, z) = \sigma_{xx}(-a, z). \quad (17)$$

Fig. 2 Transverse shear stresses at the boundary of an uncracked lamina

There is another boundary condition obtainable from the rotational symmetry about the vertical central axis, which is always present in the laminate, cracked or not, in general [16]. It is also observed by the loading condition as. The rotational symmetry on σ_{xx} yields the same condition (17). However, for σ_{xz} , as it is antisymmetric under this particular symmetry transformation, this symmetry requires

$$\sigma_{xz}^2 = -\sigma_{xz}^3. \quad (18)$$

Together with (26), the boundary conditions associated with shear can be given as

$$\sigma_{xz}^2 = \sigma_{xz}^3 = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \sigma_{xz}(+a, z) = \sigma_{xz}(-a, z) = 0. \quad (19)$$

With (13) for cracked laminae and (19) for uncracked laminae, it can be seen that the transverse shear stress at $x = \pm a$ vanishes in all laminae of the laminate, cracked and uncracked. This results in the fact that the first order derivative of ϕ_l vanishes at $x = \pm a$ for every lamina, given the expression of σ_{xz} as in (7).

Using (7), the boundary conditions in terms of stresses as obtained above can be expressed in terms of ϕ . They are summarised below. For each cracked lamina, the conditions in (13) give four boundary conditions as follows.

$$\phi_i(\pm a) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \phi_i'(\pm a) = 0. \quad (20)$$

For an uncracked lamina, (16) and (19) together give 3 boundary conditions as follow.

$$\phi_i(+a) - \phi_i(-a) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \phi_i'(+a) = \phi_i'(-a) = 0 \quad (22)$$

the first condition in (21) being in form of equation.

The physical construction of the problem does not offer any more traction boundary condition. As a result, there will not be sufficient boundary conditions directly from the physical conditions. If all the uncracked laminae can be eliminated using (8), one does not have to worry about the lack of boundary conditions, as in [2,12,13]. Without an extra boundary condition for an uncracked lamina, the applicability of all existing approaches in the literature, except those displacement-based ones, such as finite strips [5] and finite elements, will be limited to cases having maximum of two uncracked laminae. Such applicability has been summarised graphically in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Applicability of conventional cracked laminate analysis methods

For any laminate having more than two uncracked laminae, an extension is required in terms of boundary conditions. It is clear now that the limiting factor for applications of the cracked laminate analysis as originally proposed [2] to more general laminates does not result from the number of cracked laminae but the number of uncracked laminae. Unless all uncracked laminae are eliminated using (8), there is a shortfall of one boundary condition for each independent uncracked lamina.

DERIVATION OF NATURAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

As Euler's equations are derived using variational calculus, terms also emerge which take their values at boundaries resulting from steps of integration by parts. This leads to boundary conditions, called natural boundary conditions in variational principles. For the current problem with the functional given in (9), the natural boundary conditions obtained directly from the variational calculus are [17-18]

$$\left[\frac{\partial F}{\partial \{\phi\}} - \frac{d}{dx} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \{\phi''\}} \right]_{+a} - \left[\frac{\partial F}{\partial \{\phi\}} - \frac{d}{dx} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \{\phi''\}} \right]_{-a} = 0. \quad (22)$$

Given F as expressed in (9), the natural boundary conditions in (22) can be obtained as

$$[B_2] (\{\phi''(+a)\} - \{\phi''(-a)\}) + [B_3] (\{\phi'''(+a)\} - \{\phi'''(-a)\}) = 0 \quad (23)$$

$$\text{where } [B_2] = [C^{12}] - [C^{12}]^T \quad \text{and} \quad [B_3] = [C^{22}]. \quad (24)$$

In obtaining (23), use has been made of physical boundary conditions (21) and terms with a factor of $\{\phi(+a)\} - \{\phi(-a)\}$ or $\{\phi'(+a)\} - \{\phi'(-a)\}$ have been dropped. $[B_2]$ is associated with off-axis laminae and it disappears for cross-ply laminates. Apparently, (23) applies only to independent uncracked laminae.

(21) and (23) together provide a complete set of boundary conditions, i.e. four for each uncracked lamina, except those which have been eliminated using conditions (8). The above boundary conditions are obtained as a part of variational process and hence mathematically rigorous. The physical meaning is however not obvious. It is therefore not easily obtainable from one's intuition based on physical appearance of the laminate.

The natural boundary conditions in (23) are a consequence of variational principle.

EXAMPLE

Consider a $[0_p/90_q/0_r]_s$ laminate with both 90° plies cracked under uniaxial tension as shown in Fig. 4, where only a symmetry half is shown and the analysis will be made on the bottom half of the laminate. In what follows, the orthotropy of all laminae involved in the laminate coordinate system will be assumed.

Fig. 4 $[0_p/90_q/0_r]_s$ laminate (half) with both 90° plies cracked under uniaxial tension

The compliance matrix employed in (1) can be obtained for either plane stress or plane strain. Although the differences between them are only associated with Poisson ratios, they are not always insignificant. It should be pointed out that, although either plane strain or plane stress can be used to make mathematical sense and the plane stress formulation has been commonly followed in the literature following [2] blindly sometimes, it is however by no means the most reasonable choice. A plane stress state is realised when the laminate is infinitely narrow in the y -direction while plane strain corresponds to the opposite, i.e. infinitely wide. One may argue that neither is realistic. However, the latter can be reasonably achieved with appropriate length and constraints in the y -direction, while the former simply does not have any realistic significance. The

most relevant idealisation would be a generalised plane strain state with zero membrane force in the y -direction [14], which will be pursued in future.

For comparison, the case of $[0^\circ/90^\circ_2/0^\circ]$ laminate in [2] is considered. The present theory reproduces the result [2] if the plane stress compliances are used. To have a case as close to this as possible but beyond applicability of the original approach in [2], the same laminate is doubled in layup to give a $[0^\circ/90^\circ_2/0^\circ]_s$ with everything else remaining the same. Plane strain is assumed. For comparison purposes, Hashin's results have also been reproduced under plane strain condition.

Stresses at several typical locations are plotted in Fig. 5 (present results in black) and compared with those from the case of $[0^\circ/90^\circ_2/0^\circ]$ based on [2] (in grey). They have all been normalised with respect to the direct stress in the x -direction in the 90° lamina before cracking, which is obtained from the classic laminate theory. Most of the features and trends as obtained from Hashin's [2] analysis are observed here. The most pronounced difference is in the magnitude of the transverse direct stress σ_{zz} along the mid plane of the cracked lamina, where the present result shows a significant reduction.

Fig. 5 Comparison between the results from $[0^\circ/90^\circ_2/0^\circ]_s$ and $[0^\circ/90^\circ_2/0^\circ]$ laminates

To highlight the differences, the transverse shear stress σ_{xz} along the mid plane of the cracked lamina and the transverse direct stress σ_{zz} on the mid plane of the central 0°_2 lamina, i.e. the plane of symmetry of the laminate, are plotted in Fig. 6. Had the laminate layup not been doubled, these stresses would both vanish identically. The transverse shear stress σ_{xz} along the mid plane of the cracked lamina does not vanish here, although it is relatively small in magnitude. This implies that within the half laminate, the stress distributions are no longer symmetric about the mid plane of the half laminate, even though the layup of the half laminate possesses such symmetry. The mid plane of the central 0°_2 lamina corresponds to the top surface of the $[0^\circ/90^\circ_2/0^\circ]$ laminate in Hashin's case [2] where it was a free surface and hence σ_{zz} vanished identically. It is not a free surface here anymore. This suggests that half of a $[0^\circ/90^\circ_2/0^\circ]_s$ laminate do not behave in the same way as a $[0^\circ/90^\circ_2/0^\circ]$ laminate, even though it would according to the classic laminate theory, had the laminate not cracked.

Fig. 6 Stresses in $[0^\circ/90^\circ_2/0^\circ]_s$ in contrast with the behaviour of $[0^\circ/90^\circ_2/0^\circ]$

To reveal the different contributions from inner and outer uncracked layers, percentage variations from Hashin's result [2] in axial stress σ_{xx} in these two layers $100\% \times (\sigma_{xx}^{(1)\text{present}} - \sigma_{xx}^{(\text{uncracked})\text{Hashin}}) / \sigma_1$ and $100\% \times (\sigma_{xx}^{(3)\text{present}} - \sigma_{xx}^{(\text{uncracked})\text{Hashin}}) / \sigma_3$ have been plotted in Fig 7. In the virgin laminate, these two laminae take equal share of stress according to the classic laminate theory. On the emergence of cracks in the 90° laminae, a difference can be found in between. The inner uncracked lamina (dotted) takes slightly a higher share than the outer one (solid) around the crack tip. This agrees with the consideration that the outer lamina allows a deformation mechanism for the material to move inwards towards the cracked lamina, which eases the stress concentration there to an extent, while the inner lamina lacks such mechanism due to the symmetry of the laminate. Away from crack tip, the trend reverses. This is the consequence of compatibility requirement so that overall stretching in both laminae remains the same. Between these two curves in Fig. 7 is a curve (dashed) for the same stress but in the cracked lamina and converted as $100\% \times (\sigma_2 - \sigma_{xx}^{(2)\text{present}}) / \sigma_1$. This is so introduced that it can be plotted on the same side of the abscissa axis as the other two curves for direct comparison. Equilibrium requires that this value be the average of the other two, i.e. stress in the 90° lamina redistributes to the 0° laminae after cracking, which has obviously been satisfied correctly as a check on the results.

Fig. 6 Relative axial stresses in all laminae

One can apply the analysis to more cases but it will not be pursued here in this paper. However, with the example given above, it is sufficient to demonstrate that the restriction present in Hashin's analysis has been removed successfully by supplementing natural boundary conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

The obstacle in the application of Hashin's analysis [2] to more general problems has been identified, which is responsible for the lack of progress in this respect. The limiting factor on possible extensions is the lack of boundary conditions from the physical problem. This difficulty can be overcome by incorporating natural boundary conditions available from the variational calculus, which are mathematically sound but not physically apparent and hence cannot be obtained simply from physical construction of the problem intuitively. They have been derived and, as a result, the applicability of the approach has been extended fundamentally. An application has been made to a problem to demonstrate the use of such natural boundary conditions without which the problem could not be dealt with in the framework of Hashin's original approach [2].

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